

BABOTS

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The design and control of small swarming
biological animal robots*

Mechanistic models of BABots swarms

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1 Introduction

This deliverable reports on the progress achieved within Work Package WP3 concerning the development of mechanistic models of collective behaviour in BABots, with a primary focus on modelling *C. elegans* behaviours. The objective of this work is to establish quantitative and predictive frameworks that link individual-level behavioural dynamics to emergent swarm-level properties, combining data-driven methodologies with theoretical and computational modelling approaches.

The document is organised as follows. Section 2 presents a behavioural classification framework tailored to limited-visibility environments, in which discrete locomotory states are identified from experimental trajectory data and formalised through a probabilistic state-transition model influenced by external stimuli. Section 3 introduces a data-driven analysis of density-dependent random walks, examining how local population density modulates motion patterns and diffusion characteristics. Section 4 focuses on social inference and interaction metrics, proposing quantitative tools to characterise inter-individual interactions and information flow within worm populations. Section 5 describes an individual-based modelling framework for collective chemotaxis, integrating behavioural rules, sensory inputs, and environmental gradients to reproduce and analyse emergent collective dynamics. Taken together, these sections provide a complementary set of approaches that contribute to the overarching goal of understanding, modelling, and ultimately controlling collective behaviours in biological systems within the BABots framework.

This deliverable represents work in progress. The methodologies and results presented herein are preliminary and will be further developed, validated, and consolidated over the next six months, leading to more comprehensive analyses and fully validated models.

2 Behavioural classification for limited-visibility environments

This section describes the development of a model for the *C. elegans* that is able to link individual and collective behaviour. To this end, we develop a methodology to extract discrete behavioural states from a set of tracks of worms in varying environmental conditions. In particular, each behavioural state defines a stereotyped representation of the worm displacement, which we assume to be qualitatively common across environmental conditions. On the other hand, we assume transitions between states to be probabilistic and possibly influenced by an external stimulus. Hence, we build a Probabilistic Finite-State Machine (PFSM) to model the transition rates between behavioural states, which are estimated from data. Our methodology requires only one point of the worm body to be tracked through time. In particular, we use tracks of individual worms that are on-food, off-food and performing chemotaxis. Since we assume behavioural states to be common across conditions, we estimate them from the ensemble of data from the three conditions, while the transition rates between states are influenced by the stimulus. In the off-food condition, no measurable signal is present, while in the on-food condition, food density and consumption have not been measured. On the other hand, in the chemotaxis condition, we know all the parameters necessary to estimate the chemical gradient concentration by leveraging a diffusion model. Hence, the most informative analysis comes from how the transition rates differ between the off-food and the chemotaxis conditions,

Figure 1: (A) Overview of the behavioural classification pipeline. (B) Model selection rule: we select the model with the lowest number of components while its performance (given by the Bayesian Information Criterion) is within 1 standard deviation of the best model.

as the two represent an undirected and a directed exploration strategy, respectively, while the on-food condition represents an exploitation strategy. Finally, we are able to find a quantitative relationship between the sensed chemical gradient and the transition probabilities.

2.1 Methods

2.1.1 Behavioural states

An overview of our pipeline can be found in Figure 1A. The pipeline analyses individual worm tracks by taking as input a set of x, y, t points. We first apply a Savitzky-Golay filter on the positions (order=1, window size=5) to get rid of tracking noise. Then, for each point, we define a set of features: speed, angle change, angular concordance, curvature and re-sampled angle change. Speed is defined as the mean velocity magnitude over 10 consecutive frames, while the angle change is defined as the angle between two consecutive displacement vectors. Angular concordance is computed as the magnitude of the mean cosine and sine of 15 consecutive angles, while curvature as the sum of the absolute values of angles. The re-sampled angle change is computed as the minimum angle between consecutive points on the trajectory such that the points have a distance of 0.1mm. We then subsample all features to 3fps and balance the data across conditions so that all conditions have the same amount of data. Then, we apply a Yeo-Johnson power transform and scale to unit variance in order to normalise and standardise the features.

After computing the features, we note that a fundamental behaviour that can be observed in the worm is reversing. Reversals are locomotory patterns in which a worm moves backwards, tail first. To detect them, we locate points where the re-sampled angle change is above 2rad [6]. The remaining points are classified by training a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) on the features (re-sampled angle change has been omitted), where we vary the number of components from 2 to 9. Then, we select the model with the lowest number of components while its performance is

Figure 2: SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) applied to the XGBoost model trained to predict state labels from features. Plots indicate the importance of features values for the classifier to recognise state 0 (A), 1 (B), 2 (C) and 3 (D).

within 1 standard deviation of the best model. We measure performance through the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC).

To investigate further how features values are correlated to the behavioural states, we train a multi-class XGBoost classifier on the features to predict state labels. The training is performed by tuning the hyperparameters through Bayesian optimisation, with stratified cross-validation. The training data consists of 80% of all the features and the relative state labels. Hence, our classifier learns to predict behavioural state labels (dashed line in Figure 1A) from the features.

In order to estimate transition probabilities between behavioural states, we simply count the transitions $i \rightarrow j$ and normalise it by the total occurrences of i . These probabilities are expected to be different across environmental conditions. In particular, the on-food and the off-food conditions are expected to have time-invariant transition probabilities. On the other hand, during chemotaxis, the probabilities are linked to the concentration of the chemical, hence rendering the probabilities time dependant.

We show the resulting PFSM with edge thickness proportional to transition probabilities in Figure 3.

2.1.2 Odour diffusion

During chemotaxis, a worm is placed at a fixed distance from a drop of diacetyl. The diacetyl diffuses through the plate and the worm feels the gradient, climbing it. To model the chemical diffusion, we leverage the diacetyl diffusion equation:

$$C(x, y, t) = C_{max} e^{-\frac{r(x,y)}{4Dt}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 3: Probabilistic finite state machine obtained from all data. Nodes represent behavioural states, edges transition between states. Transition rates are proportional to edge thickness.

where $C_{max} = 0.01$, $D = 2.52mm^2/s$ is the diacetyl diffusion constant [5] and

$$r(x, y) = (x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2 \quad (2)$$

is distance from the odour source (x_0, y_0) . This allows us to estimate the chemical concentration $C(x, y, t)$ perceived by the worm at each point. For the sake of simplicity, we omit x, y in the notation as they depend on time $(x(t), y(t))$. Moreover, we are able to estimate the instantaneous change in concentration $\Delta C(t) = C(t) - C(t - 1)$, which numerically represents whether the worm is climbing or descending the gradient at any time $t \neq 0$. However, the estimate of ΔC is noisy because our data is subsampled at 3fps. Hence, we use the integrated gradient $\Delta C_{int}(t)$:

$$\Delta C_{int}(t) = \sum_{k \in [t-\tau, t]} \Delta C(k) = \Delta C(t) - \Delta C(t - \tau) \quad (3)$$

where τ is a proxy for the memory of the worm. However, we must note that τ could be transition specific, meaning that the worm needs to collect a different amount of evidence for each transition. To verify this, we first define a maximum memory for the system ($\tau_{max} = 210$ frames). Next, for each transition $i \rightarrow j$ such that i happens at time k , we construct the set of ΔC values from $k - \tau_{max}$ to k . Formally, given the ordered set S of states, we want to find the series $A_{i,j}$ of perceived changes in the gradient preceding each transition i, j :

$$A_{i,j} = \{\Delta C(t) \forall t \in [k - \tau_{max}, k] | i(k) \in S \wedge j(k + 1) \in S\} \quad (4)$$

For each transition, we will have a set of series $\mathbf{T}_{i,j} = \{A_{i,j}^1 \dots A_{i,j}^c\}$ with cardinality c equal to the number of times that transition happens. If a transition happens at a time $t < \tau_{max}$, we

set $\Delta C(t) = 0$. Next, we compute the kernel $K_{i,j}$ as the mean of all ΔC values experienced at transition i, j :

$$K_{i,j}(t) = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{T}_{i,j}|} \sum_{A_{i,j} \in \mathbf{T}_{i,j}} A_{i,j}(t) \quad (5)$$

By computing $K_{i,j}(t) \forall t \in [-\tau_{max}, 0]$, we obtain the mean ΔC history kernel $\mathbf{K}_{i,j}$ that precedes each transition. This history allows us to estimate the autocorrelation between subsequent ΔC values. In particular, for each transition $i \rightarrow j$, we look at the autocorrelation function acf of $\mathbf{K}_{i,j}$. Thus, we define the maximum memory for a transition $\tau_{i,j}$ as the e-folding time of the autocorrelation function of the history:

$$\tau_{i,j} = \max \left(6, \min_{\tau} \text{acf}(\mathbf{K}_{i,j}(\tau)) \leq \frac{1}{e} \right) \quad (6)$$

Where 6 frames are equivalent to 2 seconds, the minimum memory proxy we decide to set. We can now extend Equation 3 to specify that $\Delta C_{int}(t)$ is transition specific:

$$\Delta C_{int}^{i,j}(t) = \Delta C(t) - \Delta C(t - \tau_{i,j}) \quad (7)$$

Therefore, we can collect the set of $\Delta \mathbf{C}_{int}^{i,j}$ for each transition and attempt to find the probability function $p(i \rightarrow j | \Delta \mathbf{C}_{int}^{i,j})$. To this end, we opted for a multinomial logistic regression fit on each source state i , with a minimum number of observed transitions set to 20. We clip the set $\Delta \mathbf{C}_{int}^{i,j}$ to the range $[p1, p99]$, corresponding to the first and 99th percentile of the distribution so to exclude outliers. Then, we standardised the values to unit variance and performed the fit using class balancing to account for spurious transitions.

2.2 Results

2.2.1 State properties

In this section, we present the behavioural states obtained from our pipeline, together with their properties. We show our model selection in Figure 1B. The Gaussian Mixture Model with the lowest BIC is the one with 9 components, however we select the GMM with 3 components as it is the least complex model with a comparable BIC to the best GMM. The reasoning is that, in general, by increasing the number of components, the performance improves together with the complexity of the model, while we seek the simplest model with a comparable performance to the best model. Hence, the set of behavioural states is given by the reversal state, which was flagged manually via thresholding on the re-sampled angle change, and the 3 states found by the GMM. Next, we apply SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) to the XGBoost classifier and plot their values in Figure 2. State 0 corresponds to the reversal state (Figure 2A). State 1 is associated to low speed and high curvature (Figure 2B), while state 2 is associated to high speed and low curvature (Figure 2C). Hence, we refer to these states as "Walk" and "Run", respectively. The last state is characterised by intermediate speed and intermediate angle change (Figure 2D), thus we refer to this state as "Arc".

Next, we compare the behavioural states features and transition rates across experimental conditions. In the on-food condition, worms usually slow down, decreasing their motor activity,

Figure 4: Angle change (A) and speed (B) distributions across behavioural states for all environmental conditions. Each state shows the relative proportion of data that in that condition. Reversals (cluster 0) and Walk (cluster 1) are more frequent in the on-food condition, while states Run (cluster 2) and Arc (cluster 3) are more frequent in the off-food and chemotaxis conditions.

Figure 5: Statistically significant differences in feature distributions across experimental conditions. In particular, differences in: speed distribution in the Reversal state between on-food and off-food (A); speed distribution in the Run state between off-food and chemotaxis (B); angle change distribution in the Arc state between off-food and chemotaxis (C).

while during chemotaxis and in the off-food condition, we expect the motor activity to increase. Thus, although behavioural states represent common locomotory primitives, the specific shape and median values of the features might change across environmental conditions, shifting or distorting the distributions. Hence, we are interested in understanding whether the experimental condition influences the feature distributions. In particular, we compare the speed and angle change distributions for each behavioural state across conditions. We show the angle change and speed distributions across behavioural states and conditions in Figure 4. All the statistically significant differences were computed via a pairwise Mann-Whitney U test ($p < 1e - 5$). We find that the on-food speed distribution is consistently lower than the other conditions in all states (see Figure 5A for an example). Similarly, the worm moves slower in the off-food condition than during chemotaxis in states Run and Arc, as per Figure 5B (Arc omitted). Moreover, worms tend to have the highest angle change during Reversals in the on-food condition. On the other hand, during Arcs, the on-food angle change is the lowest, while the off-food angle change is higher than during chemotaxis (see Figure 5C).

Figure 6: (A) Dwell-time comparison between on-food, off-food and chemotaxis conditions. (B) Difference between transition rates during chemotaxis and off-food. Cells marked with a star have at least 30 transitions in both conditions. Specific transition rates for (C) the off-food condition, (D) the chemotaxis condition and (E) the on-food condition.

Furthermore, we are interested in understanding whether the presence of an environmental cue during chemotaxis influences the state dwell-time. To this end, we compute the dwell-time distributions for each state s as the set of lengths of subsequent frames labelled s . We show the distributions of dwell-times for each state separated between conditions in Figure 6(A). For the sake of brevity, we focus only on the analysis of the chemotaxis and off-food conditions. The Reversal and Walk state dwell-times are consistently higher in the off-food condition, which is in line with an undirected search strategy. On the other hand, the Run state has longer dwell-times during chemotaxis, which is in line with a directed search strategy. The Arc state dwell-times can be decomposed into two. The lower dwell-times (< 5 frames) are more frequent during chemotaxis, while the higher ones (≥ 5) are more frequent in the off-food condition.

Since the dwell-time distribution varies across conditions, we construct a transition matrix that allows self-loops. We compare the transition matrices of the off-food condition and during

Figure 7: Transition probabilities as a function of the integrated gradient computed by fitting a multinomial logistic regression on each source state i : Reversal (A), Run (B) and Arc (C). State Walk does not have a sufficient amount of transitions during chemotaxis, hence we do not fit a multinomial regression on it.

chemotaxis, and display it in Figure 6B. We impose a lower bound of 30 transitions in each condition for the difference to be significant and mark those cells with a star symbol. The transition rates across conditions are in Figures 6(C-E).

2.2.2 Modulation of transitions

The goal of this section is to understand how the presence of a chemical gradient influences state transitions. In particular, we want to find $p(i \rightarrow j | \Delta C_{int})$ for each state i, j (see Section 2.1.2 for details). With the $\tau_{i,j}$ estimated from the ΔC autocorrelation function, we are able to fit a multinomial logistic regression model with class balancing for each source state i and thus estimate $p(i \rightarrow j | \Delta C_{int})$. We show the resulting probabilities in Figure 7. In particular, in Figure 7A, we observe that based on the sign of the integrated gradient, worms tend to remain in the Reversal state for negative values, while they tend to transition to the Arc state for positive values. Figure 7B shows that worms tend to remain in the Run state for $\Delta C_{int} > 0$ and transition more frequently to the Arc and Reversal states for $\Delta C_{int} < 0$. Finally, in Figure 7C we can observe a more modest modulation from the Arc state: worms tend to transition to the “Run” state for $\Delta C_{int} > 0$ and transition more frequently to the Reversal state and to itself for $\Delta C_{int} < 0$.

From these results, we can observe that during chemotaxis, a worm mainly modulates tran-

sitions from the Reversal and Run states. In particular, when it is in the Reversal state and encounters an increase in the integrated gradient, it will most likely Arc. From the Arc state, if the positive trend is sustained, the worm transitions to the Run state. On the other hand, from the Run state, the worm will either enter the Reversal or Arc state for negative gradients. While in the Arc state, the angle change distribution peaks at 0 and at 1.5rad, as from Figure 5C. Moreover, by comparing the distributions of angle changes in the Arc state, we find that a positive ΔC_{int} triggers more often (Mann-Whitney U test, $p < 1e - 6$) reorientations at 1.5rad than negative values, which seem to suppress the reorientation. Hence, the Arc state is used as a reorientation mechanism which happens after a reversal.

2.3 Future work

Our methodology requires only one point of the worm body to be tracked, thus we expect to be able to apply it to data from experiments in which one worm, marked through a green fluorescent protein on its pharynx, is tracked within a collective of unmarked worms. Hence, we will be able to measure how the presence of other worms influences the individual decisions. The model using state transitions as a logistic function of the accumulated signal will first be validated by comparing the transition rates of a set of agents within a simulated chemotaxis environment with those of the data from the chemotaxis condition. Then, it will be used to infer through an evolutionary strategy which parameters are needed to induce a specific collective behaviour. As a proof of concept, a group of agents will be evolved so that they display a diffusion process. The actual parameters that govern wild type *C. elegans* will be estimated by fitting a similar regression model to transitions extrapolated from the tracks of marked worms within collectives. Finally, we will leverage these results with a comparative analysis on the probability transition rates of worms within collectives and in the presence of an attractive odour. Our results will help in determining which particular behavioural transitions are more desirable to bring forward a specific collective behaviour.

3 Data-driven density-dependent random walks in *C. elegans*

The goal of this activity is to accurately model the worms' random motion as a function of variations in local population density. To the best of our knowledge, there are no data-driven models that account for local worm density, and approaches that leverage statistical physics to detect anomalous diffusion will be leveraged [2, 9, 3]. As a first step to accomplish this task, the MPG has conducted a series of experiments in which groups of unrestrained *C. elegans* are observed under a microscope. The activity of these free-moving worms is recorded using a dual-color imaging system (refer to Deliverable D1.2). This setup allows us to label the worms with fluorescent proteins in two distinct colors, enabling us to distinguish focal individuals from the rest of the population. In the following sections, we describe two approaches we have used to track multiple focal individuals and their associated local density. Once the video is recorded, tracking the focal individuals, estimating their local velocity, and determining corresponding population density for the focal worms are accomplished using PharaGlow, a tool developed by MPG, along with other post-processing tools. Based on this data, we will develop a random walk model that accounts for varying population densities.

3.1 Experimental setups and local density estimation

For our experimental setups, we divided the worm population into two groups in a 1 : 10 ratio: a focal group and a swarm group from which local densities were computed. The worms were recorded using a fluorescence microscope and tagged with two different proteins to distinguish focal individuals from those in the swarm. Specifically, focal worms expressed *mCherry* under the *myo-2* promoter (pharyngeal marker), while swarm worms expressed *GFP* targeted to mitochondria under the *myo-3* promoter (a muscle marker). To date, we have worked exclusively with homogeneous populations of worms to establish baseline models for diverse *C. elegans* strains.

For the **first set of experiments**, we followed an asynchronous approach (see Figure 8), alternating the excitation light wavelength between blue to excite *GFP* and record swarm activity, and yellow-green to excite *mCherry* and track focal individuals. By uncoupling the recording of individual and swarm activity, this approach enabled tracking of a large number of focal individuals. As a reference, in the reported experiment, $\sim 2,400$ focal worms expressed *mCherry* in the pharynx, while the swarm, $\sim 24,000$ expressed *GFP* in the body wall. However, the temporal asynchrony between swarm and individual recordings poses a challenge for accurately estimating local density around focal individuals.

Figure 8: **Top:** Timeline for asynchronous recording of swarm and focal individuals, switching between *swarm* and *individual* periods. **Bottom:** Superposition of focal worms activity (in red) and swarm (in green). Notice that while the tracks for the focal worms’ activity correspond to a full *individual* period, the swarm is only the last frame from the preceding *swarm* period.

In our analyses, we used the average pixel intensity within a 5×5 grid centered on the focal worm’s centroid as a proxy for local density. To account for the temporal offset between *swarm* and *individual* recordings, we applied linear interpolation between the last swarm image of the preceding interval and the first image of the subsequent interval.

For the **second set of experiments**, we adopted a different approach to avoid complications arising from temporal asynchrony in local density estimation. In this case, we used constant dual-color illumination (see Figure 9) to visualize both worm groups simultaneously. We also reduced the number of worms under the microscope to $\sim 5,000$, while maintaining a 1 : 10 ratio between focal individuals and the swarm. All experiments were conducted with off food

Figure 9: (A) Original BGR image obtained under dual-color illumination. (B) Grayscale image representation of the green channel after histogram equalization.

N2 individuals and lasted 30 minutes. Recordings were acquired at 15 frames per second (fps), using $1\times$ magnification for the asynchronous set, and $0.625\times$ magnification for the dual-color experiments.

3.2 Classification based on local densities

The videos were processed using PharaGlow to extract the trajectories of the focal worms. To reduce high-frequency noise in the tracking data, the original videos were downsampled from 15 fps to 3 fps. PharaGlow employs a centroid-based tracking algorithm, returning the coordinates of all detected pharynges at each frame. As described above, local density was estimated as the average pixel intensity within a 5×5 grid centered on the focal worm's centroid.

The trajectories were segmented into tracklets, each of which was assigned the average local density during its duration. Individual trajectories range from a few seconds to several minutes. To determine the appropriate tracklet length, we conducted a preliminary analysis of the velocity autocorrelation to ensure that relevant temporal correlations in the worm motion are preserved. From this analysis, we selected a tracklet duration of 40 seconds.

We divided the tracklets into two groups based on their mean local density using k-means clustering. Figure 10 shows the distribution of mean local densities for (A) each individual recording in the asynchronous dataset, and (B) the resulting distribution after classification into two groups. Similarly, Figure 11 shows (A) the original distribution for a full 30-minute recording from the second set of experiments and (B) the distribution after classification. It is important to note that the relationship between pixel intensity and local density differs between the two experimental setups. In the asynchronous experiments, higher pixel intensity corresponds to higher local density, whereas in the dual-color experiments, the opposite holds (see Figures 8 and 9); pixel intensity values were inverted for the second set of experiments before analysis.

Figure 10: (A) Distribution of mean local densities for the tracklets found on each swarm recording. (B) Distribution of local densities after classification, with cluster 0 (in blue) corresponding to high-density and cluster 1 (in red) to low-density.

Figure 11: (A) Distribution of mean local densities for a full 30-minute recording. (B) Distribution of local densities after classification, with cluster 0 (in blue) corresponding to high-density and cluster 1 (in red) to low-density.

3.3 Ensembles characterization

To investigate differences in motion patterns between the two classes and their dependence on local density, we computed two metrics for each ensemble.

Mean squared displacement

We computed the mean squared displacement (MSD) for each ensemble, which quantifies how far the worm spreads from its starting position over time and is commonly used to characterize diffusive behavior. The MSD is computed as follows:

$$\langle MSD(\tau) \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\left| x^k(\tau) - x^k(0) \right| \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

Under high-density conditions, worm motion is expected to be approximately Brownian, corresponding to a diffusion coefficient close to 1 (normal diffusion). In contrast, under low-density conditions, trajectories are expected to exhibit superdiffusive behavior, with an exponent greater than 1, indicating more persistent, directed motion. Figure 12 shows the MSD plots for the ensembles in (A) asynchronous recordings, and (B) the dual-color recordings. As expected, the high-density classes (cluster 0) exhibit exponents close to 1, while the low-density classes show significantly larger exponents, a sign of more directed motion.

Velocity correlation

We computed the autocorrelation of velocities (V_{ac}) for each ensemble in the x - and y - directions, which quantifies the persistence in directional motion. The V_{ac} is computed as follows:

$$\langle v_{corr,x}(\tau) \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (v_{x,k}(\tau) - v_{x,k}(0)) \quad (9)$$

Figure 12: Mean squared displacement curves for high-density and low-density ensembles are shown in blue and red, respectively for (A) asynchronous recordings, and (B) dual-color recordings.

Figure 13: Vac curves for the x - and y - are shown in solid and semi-transparent colors, respectively, while V_{cc} curves are shown in gray, for (A) asynchronous recordings, and (B) dual-color recordings.

In addition, we computed the cross-correlation (V_{cc}) between velocity components to assess potential coupling between directions. The V_{cc} is computed as follows:

$$\langle v_{cross,xy}(\tau) \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (v_{x,k}(\tau) - v_{y,k}(0)) \quad (10)$$

As with the MSD analysis, high-density tracklets are expected to exhibit little to no temporal correlation, whereas low-density tracklets should display stronger persistence. Figure 13 shows the velocity correlation functions for the ensembles in (A) asynchronous recordings and in (B) dual-color recordings. Consistent with the MSD results, high-density ensembles (cluster 0) exhibit negligible correlation even at short lag times. In contrast, low-density ensembles (cluster 1) exhibit significant temporal correlations in both directions, extending beyond 10 seconds. Additionally, no significant cross-correlation between velocity components was found in any scenario, indicating no coupling between directions.

3.4 Discussion and future work

The results presented in this section show strong consistency between the asynchronous and dual-color experiments, with both approaches revealing a clear distinction between high- and

low-density scenarios. In dense conditions, the worms exhibit normal diffusion, whereas in sparse conditions, they exhibit superdiffusivity. Additionally, the absence of cross-correlation between velocity components suggests that motion in both directions can be modeled independently, supporting the use of simplified stochastic frameworks and laying the groundwork for developing a model that accurately describes the motion patterns of *C. elegans* as a function of local population density.

Future work will extend this analysis to other *C. elegans* strains, first using homogeneous populations and then heterogeneous ones, to evaluate whether these motion patterns and the proposed modeling approach generalize across distinct population compositions. We also plan to model the worm trajectories using stochastic Langevin equations. In addition, rather than restricting the analysis to two density classes, we will investigate whether multiple behavioral regimes can be identified by examining local-density statistics over tracklets, including transitions between regimes. Finally, high-resolution recordings will enable the estimation of nematic order parameters, providing a complementary classification based on local alignment and collective motion.

4 Social inference and interaction metrics

This work was conducted to identify robust metrics for social interaction in *C. elegans* for the future application of evaluating strains developed for the BABots mission. Specifically, we aim to infer causality between local social density and the acceleration of an individual in order to determine whether it's exhibiting aggregative or dispersive behaviour and quantify such behaviour. Using dual-color imaging data collected by the MPG and tracked via PharaGlow, we characterize interactions through local density approximations. These explorations facilitate future comparisons across MPG-recorded strains and inform transfer entropy methods to derive robust non-linear interaction rules for behavioural modeling.

Tracking and density methods are detailed in Section 3. Data analyzed here stems from an experiment using approximately 5,000 *N2* individuals recorded at 15 frames per second (fps) at 0.625x magnification. The dataset spans 20,356 frames with an average of about 160 concurrent tracklets. To preserve causality and minimize bias, processing was kept minimal. A second-order Butterworth filter with a cut-off frequency of 0.1 Hz was used to eliminate high-frequency noise due to tracking errors.

4.1 Cross-correlation analysis

Preliminary analysis indicated that the relationship between acceleration (\vec{a}) and change in density ($\Delta\rho$) is highly non-linear. For that reason, they were cross-correlated in different density bins separated by the 33rd and 66th percentiles to explore the role of density in mediating the worm's response to social stimulus (see Figure 14). The experiment begins with water droplets containing *C. elegans* at high concentrations being placed in the set-up. The system is therefore at a non-stationary state at the time of recording because the initial clusters are not stable, so it was necessary to standardize both $\Delta\rho$ and \vec{a} on a frame-by-frame basis. In this way, their values represent the relative deviation from the mean of the current frame and can be more

easily compared to samples from different time points.

The null control was generated by circularly shifting $\Delta\rho$ so as to preserve its autocorrelation but disrupt its coupling with \vec{a} . This control is mostly flat with respect to lag. Notably, in each density condition there are significant peaks and/or troughs of cross-correlation that occur at generally the same lag values but have different signs.

In the low density condition, $\Delta\rho$ and \vec{a} are positively correlated at negative and positive non-zero lags, but negatively correlated at zero. This may indicate a general tendency for decreases in local densities to occur when individuals are actively dispersing in sparse regimes (and therefore accelerating). The positive correlation at positive lag shows the worms are likely actively moving to decrease their local densities, and the positive correlation at negative lag indicates the smaller but reciprocal impact individuals have on their social environment.

The middle density condition is relatively similar to the low density condition, but this pattern changes at high density. At positive and negative lags, the extrema in cross-correlation are negative, which suggests that the worms tend to stay in higher densities. It is not clear whether this is because of preference or because of steric hindrances that can limit mobility in very dense clusters. If the latter is true, then the positive time lag corresponding to the most negative correlation may be characteristic of the resistance the worms experience when entering and leaving dense clusters.

Figure 14: Cross-correlation between change in density ($\Delta\rho$) and acceleration (\vec{a}). Each plot is binned according to density percentiles (0 - 33%, 33 - 66%, and 66 - 100%). Positive lags correspond to features that occur in $\Delta\rho$ before \vec{a} , and vice versa. Envelopes correspond to 95% confidence intervals computed via bootstrapping. The orange envelope is a circularly-shifted null such that autocorrelation in $\Delta\rho$ is preserved but is no longer coupled to \vec{a} . Both change in density and acceleration are z-scored frame-wise to account for the non-stationarity of the data.

4.2 Event-triggered speed analysis

To further interpret the results of Figure 14, we used an event-based approach in order to observe how the median \vec{a} precedes and follows instances of sharp increase (“Entry”) and decrease (“Exit”) in $\Delta\rho$. These events are meant to correspond with entries into and exits from dense clusters. Specifically, frames were identified at which the gradient of $\Delta\rho$ was larger than

a threshold of 0.1 and the median \vec{a} of the segments of \vec{a} surrounding each event was computed as a function of relative time. Subsequent event triggers within 10 frames of each other were excluded to avoid oversampling the same event. Like before, \vec{a} and $\Delta\rho$ were z-scored within their frames so as to allow data from throughout the whole experiment to be compiled without some drifting bias.

Figure 15: Median acceleration (z-scored frame-wise) preceding and following “Entry” and “Exit” events. “Entry” and “Exit” events are defined as frames in which the gradient of z-scored $\Delta\rho$ is above or below (respectively) a threshold which was set to be 0.1. As in Figure 14, the data is partitioned according to density percentile across different rows, and the columns correspond to “Entry” versus “Exit” events. The blue line is the original data and the blue envelope is its corresponding 95% confidence interval. The orange line and envelop represent the shuffled null in which event triggers were randomized so as to decouple the gradient of $\Delta\rho$ with \vec{a} .

As was done previously, the data was partitioned into bins of local density so as to observe the density-dependent effects from a different angle. There are significant peaks in \vec{a} preceding the event trigger, followed by a drop in \vec{a} following. In the high density regime, the peaks and troughs of \vec{a} are less pronounced and variable, but the pattern is very conserved across densities and even, surprisingly, symmetric across event types.

At high densities, one might expect that individuals may accelerate in order to join clusters and

that once having done so, they would slow down (perhaps due to hindrance). Similarly, one could argue that during "escape-like" behaviours, worms might accelerate in order to leave a cluster, after which they wouldn't need to move as fast any more. This could explain the event symmetry, but more evidence is needed. The different lag positions of the 'slowing-down' trough weakly point in this direction, as the minimum acceleration happens earlier in the "Entry" condition than the "Exit" condition and may hint at there behind a different mechanism behind this.

4.3 Discussion and strain evaluation benchmarking

The results presented here establish a quantitative baseline for the wild-type *N2* response to local crowding, and will serve as important groundwork to further refine our understand of how locusts respond to social stimuli according to their current environments. For the BABots mission, metrics like the peak correlation lag and perhaps the slope of \bar{a} across "Entry" and "Exit" events will allow for the differentiation of social "sensitivity" across strains. We predict that more social or engineered strains may exhibit:

1. **Higher acceleration:** The acceleration peaks observed preceding "Entry" events in *N2* may remain be larger in the high density regime in social mutants, indicating lower sensitivity to extreme densities.
2. **Increased interaction lags:** While *N2* exhibits a near-instantaneous response (lag ≈ 0.5 s) to changes in density, strains with complex signalling (e.g., pheromone-mediated) may show broad correlation peaks at higher lags, reflecting longer-range information processing.

Future work will utilize Transfer Entropy (TE) to quantify the information flow from the change in density field to individual velocity vectors. Specifically, we hypothesize that $TE_{Density \rightarrow Velocity}$ will peak at lags corresponding to the positive lags identified in Figure 14. This formal estimation of information flow will provide a robust benchmark for comparing the collective behaviour of different BABots strains.

5 Individual-based Model of Collective Chemotaxis in *C. elegans*

We implement an individual-based model to gain further insights into how social environment, inter-individual differences and chemical gradients influence collective behaviour. We focus on studying how sensory information influences individual behaviour and subsequently, the group's ability to sense and navigate gradients collectively. Moreover, this model is fine-tuned using preliminary data results, providing a closed feedback between experiments and theory.

5.1 Model implementation

The model combines elements from previous work studying *C. elegans* and fish behaviour [7, 8, 4]. The gradient navigation is implemented such that the agents employ a modified

gradient descent strategy, relying solely on local sensory information to navigate the chemical and physical environment [1]. The translation motion of the individuals can be described as a change of the centroid velocity $\mathbf{v}(t)$ which can be decomposed into speed $s(t)$ and direction of motion $\phi(t)$:

$$\mathbf{v}(t) = \frac{d\mathbf{x}(t)}{dt} = s(t)[\cos \phi(t), \sin \phi(t)] \quad (11)$$

We simulated a total number of agents N . Social interactions are introduced through a social torque and a density dependent speed:

5.1.1 Social turning with drift

We implemented a simplified version of the zonal model where we considered repulsion and attraction zones. The two social zones, repulsion and attraction, are defined by the distance radius r_r and r_a respectively. For a focal individual i and one of its neighbours j , the distance between the two is $r_{ij} = |\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|$. The preferred motion direction from the zonal model is determined as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{\text{social}} = \sum_{i \neq j}^N \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{ij}(\mathbf{r}_i, \mathbf{r}_j) \begin{cases} -\frac{\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i}{r_{ij}}, & 0 < r_{ij} \leq r_r \\ \frac{\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i}{r_{ij}}, & r_r < r_{ij} \leq r_a \\ (0, 0), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

This direction is used to calculate an effective social torque:

$$\Gamma_i = (\hat{\mathbf{v}}_i \times \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{\text{social}}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}} = v_{i,x}d_{i,y} - v_{i,y}d_{i,x} \quad (13)$$

Where $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ is the unit vector in the z-direction. The orientation dynamics are captured by a simple model that combines the previously introduced social interactions, with drift and stochastic diffusion:

$$d\phi(t)_{\text{social}} = \tau_\phi^{-1}[\alpha_i \Gamma_i - \phi(t)_{\text{social}}]dt + \sqrt{2D_\phi}dW_t \quad (14)$$

Where α_i is the social coupling strength or 'turning responsiveness', τ_ϕ the relaxation time, and the random fluctuations arise from a Wiener noise process, dW_t , with magnitude $\sqrt{2D_\phi}$.

5.1.2 Density dependent speed dynamics

The speed dynamics of each individual are described by an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck stochastic process:

$$ds(t) = \tau_s^{-1}[\mu - s(t)]dt + \sqrt{2D_s}dW_t \quad (15)$$

Which describes random fluctuations arising from a Wiener noise process, dW_t , with magnitude $\sqrt{2D_s}$, and relaxes with a time scale τ_s to an average value of $\mu = \langle s \rangle$.

Considering previous empirical observations, we incorporated a density-dependent speed, where the average speed decreases exponentially with the local density, plus an additional term.

$$\mu = \mu_0 e^{-\rho \mu_d} + \mu_c \quad (16)$$

We defined the speed at zero density as μ_0 (individuals without any neighbour inside their attraction zone), and μ_c as the baseline speed. Speed decays exponentially with an exponent μ_d , and ρ indicates the local density of worms inside the attraction zone of radius r_a surrounding an individual.

5.1.3 Gradient sensing

To determine the direction of motion of each individual ($\phi(t)$), a weighted linear combination of two directional components is applied: the individual's movement direction resulting from social interactions and the direction inferred from the odour gradient.

$$\phi(t) = \text{atan2}(w_1 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{\phi_{\text{social}}(t)} + w_2 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{\text{odour}(t)}) \quad (17)$$

Where $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{\phi_{\text{social}}}$ is the unit vector representing the individual's movement direction from social interactions, $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{\text{odour}}$ is the unit vector pointing along the odour concentration gradient, and w_1, w_2 are scalar weighting parameters indicating the relative influence of each. In the present implementation, both weights are set to $w_1 = w_2 = 1.0$, meaning social information and the odour gradient influence the individual's movement equally.

5.2 Simulation results and future work

Preliminary and qualitative simulation results indicate that social interactions can increase group performance in sensing gradients (Fig. 16), when comparing simulations of solitary individuals (low social coupling (α) values) with those of aggregating individuals (high social coupling (α) values). We have begun testing this hypothesis through experiments. Additionally, we are investigating the interplay between social interactions and pheromone signalling, focusing on how individuals perceive this information and respond to it, and its impact on the collective behaviour of the group.

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Figure 16: Model results: Trajectories of $N = 25$ agents in a 1cm^2 arena, with different values of social coupling (α). Parameter α indicates the social coupling strength: With low values individuals are solitary, and with higher values individuals are aggregating. Red circle indicates the odour source.

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